

What does Permafrost mean to you?

Inuvialuit and Gwich'in Knowledge Holders' Perceptions of a Thawing Relation

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Abstract: While climate scholarship has detailed the biophysical impacts of Arctic permafrost thaw, less attention has been paid to how permafrost is perceived and lived with. Drawing on community-based research with Inuvialuit and Gwich'in knowledge holders in the Inuvialuit and Gwich'in Settlement Regions of the Western Canadian Arctic, we argue that permafrost is more than frozen ground: it sustains mobility, subsistence, and cultural continuity; and its degradation threatens these life-giving relations. Analyzing Indigenous land users' narratives through the lenses of perception studies and infrastructure theory—and foregrounding critical Indigenous scholarship—we propose that permafrost can be understood as critical and alimentary infrastructure in a decolonial sense: an essential system and web of relations vital to societal functioning and a good life on the land. By exploring the meanings attributed to permafrost as a material, and how Indigenous land users engage with the ever-changing landscape and the acceleration of change in the Mackenzie Delta, our study highlights how permafrost thaw impacts perpetuate power imbalances of settler colonialism, as well as how Indigenous perspectives draw attention to permafrost as inseparable from land, kinship, and sustenance. This engagement expands infrastructural analysis through Indigenous epistemologies, producing new understandings of both infrastructure and environment in Arctic contexts.

Keywords: permafrost; permafrost thaw; Inuvialuit; Gwich'in; Mackenzie Delta; perception; infrastructure

Résumé: Alors que les études climatiques ont détaillé les impacts biophysiques du dégel du pergélisol arctique, une moindre attention a été accordée à la manière dont le pergélisol est perçu et vécu. En nous appuyant sur des recherches communautaires menées auprès des détenteurs de savoirs inuvialuit et gwich'in dans les régions de peuplement Inuvialuit et Gwich'in de l'Arctique canadien occidental, nous soutenons que le pergélisol est plus qu'un sol gelé : il soutient la mobilité, la subsistance et la continuité culturelle, et sa dégradation menace ces relations vitales. En analysant les récits des utilisateurs autochtones des terres à travers le prisme des études sur la perception et de la théorie des infrastructures, tout en valorisant les travaux universitaires autochtones critiques, nous proposons de considérer le pergélisol comme une infrastructure essentielle et alimentaire au sens décolonial : un système et un réseau de relations indispensables au fonctionnement de la société et à une vie agréable sur ces terres. Grâce à l'exploration des significations attribuées au pergélisol en tant que matériau, et la manière dont les utilisateurs autochtones des terres interagissent avec le paysage en constante évolution et l'accélération des changements dans le delta du Mackenzie, notre étude met en évidence la façon dont les effets du dégel du pergélisol perpétuent les déséquilibres de pouvoir du colonialisme, ainsi que la manière dont les perspectives autochtones attirent l'attention sur le pergélisol comme étant indissociable de la terre, de la parenté et de la subsistance. Cette approche élargit l'analyse des infrastructures à travers les épistémologies autochtones, produisant ainsi une nouvelle compréhension des infrastructures et de l'environnement dans un contexte arctique.

Mots clés: pergélisol ; dégel du pergélisol ; Inuvialuit ; Gwich'in ; delta du Mackenzie ; perception ; infrastructure

Introduction

What does permafrost mean to Inuvialuit and Gwich'in knowledge holders in the Mackenzie Delta of the Western Canadian Arctic? While climate scholarship has detailed the biophysical impacts of thaw, far less attention has been paid to how permafrost is perceived, valued, and lived with in this region. Drawing on community-based research with Inuvialuit and Gwich'in knowledge holders, we argue that permafrost is more than frozen ground: it is critical, alimentary, foundational infrastructure. It sustains mobility, subsistence, and cultural continuity, and its degradation threatens these life-giving relations. Perceptions of climate impacts—and specifically increased thaw—have been studied across the Arctic (for example, Carothers et al. 2014; Crate et al. 2017;

Crate 2021; Lede et al. 2021; Meyer and Sokolíčková 2024; Pearce et al. 2015; Ramage et al. 2022; Ward Jones et al. 2024), but understandings of permafrost itself remain underexamined. We address this gap by analyzing Indigenous land users' narratives through the lenses of perception, visibility and change (Chu 2014; Ingold (2000 [2011]); Krause 2021; Star 1999), and infrastructure theory (Carse 2012; Star and Ruhleder 1996). As Hetherington (2019) argues, infrastructure has become a key analytic of the Anthropocene. While we take this insight as a point of departure, our approach differs by foregrounding critical Indigenous scholarship, arguing that permafrost can be understood as critical and alimentary infrastructure (LaDuke and Cowen 2020; Spice 2018) in a decolonial sense: an essential system and web of relations vital to societal functioning and to a good life on the land (Watt-Cloutier 2015).

Increased thaw—alongside diminishing sea ice and melting glaciers, ice sheets, and snow—affects sea levels, water hazards and security, economies, and ecosystems (World Meteorological Organization 2023). Reflecting these risks, in May 2023, the World Meteorological Organization elevated the cryosphere as a top priority and termed Arctic permafrost thaw a “sleeping giant” of greenhouse gases, as permafrost stores roughly twice the carbon currently in the atmosphere. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Synthesis Report likewise identifies permafrost thaw as driving irreversible impacts on Arctic ecosystems, with consequences for the five million people living on Arctic permafrost (IPCC 2023; Ramage et al. 2021). Thaw alters soils, hydrology, flora and fauna, and biogeochemical cycles, generating hazards for local populations: infrastructure failure; disrupted mobility and supply; risks to water quality; challenges for food security; and exposure to contaminants and pathogens (Gartler et al. 2025). These changes have significant societal consequences for human and more-than-human health, ecosystems (Inuit Circumpolar Council 2015), cultural identity (Crate 2021; Crate et al. 2017; Doloisio and Vanderlinden 2020; Watt-Cloutier 2015), access to land and recreation, and financial security (Streletskiy et al. 2023). Despite growing documentation of global and local risks, the meanings attributed to permafrost as a material—particularly by Indigenous land users in the Inuvialuit Settlement Region and Gwich'in Settlement Region—remain insufficiently explored. In this article, we examine how people's perceptions relate to permafrost as part of a critical, life-sustaining infrastructure, thus contributing to what Larkin (2013) calls the “productive instability” of infrastructure as an analytic.

Regional Background and Methodology

The Mackenzie Delta (Figure 1) is marked by continuous permafrost¹, countless rivers and lakes frozen for more than six months each year, and the tree line crossing the delta (Burn and Kokelj 2009). Our research was conducted in four communities: Inuvik, Tuktoyaktuk, Aklavik and Fort McPherson. Inuvik (Inuuviik in its Inuvialuktun spelling, meaning *Living Place*), sits at the boundary of the Gwich'in and Inuvialuit Settlement Regions and has approximately three thousand residents. As the regional center, its growth in the 1970s to the 1980s was driven by oil exploration, followed by a decline after the 1986 oil price collapse and Canadian Forces Base closure. Tuktoyaktuk (Tuktuuyaqtuuq, *Place Resembling a Caribou*) is at the terminus of the Inuvik–Tuktoyaktuk Highway (ITH), with around one thousand mainly Inuvialuit residents. It faces severe shoreline erosion linked to thawing permafrost and reduced sea ice, prompting recent protection works (Loreen 2025; Whalen et al. 2022). Aklavik (Aktlarvik, *Grizzly Bear Place*), to the west of Inuvik, has approximately 650 residents of Inuvialuit and Gwich'in descent. Lastly, Fort McPherson (Teetł'it Zheh, *Town at the Head Waters*), is home to about seven hundred and fifty residents, *primarily Gwich'in First Nation*, and lies south of Inuvik along the Dempster Highway (NWT Bureau of Statistics 2024). Despite local variation, all four communities are experiencing rapid landscape change from permafrost thaw.

Building on prior work in Aklavik (Ramage et al. 2022; Timlin et al. 2022), we conducted fieldwork in fall and winter 2022–2023. Methods included informal conversations, expert interviews, and focus groups with thirty-five representatives of local organizations and regional specialists in engineering, heritage, and permafrost. Field visits took place along the Dempster Highway, the ITH, and the Mackenzie River channel between Aklavik and Inuvik. We also carried out 24 qualitative, semi-structured life-history and land-use interviews with Inuvialuit (n=16) and Gwich'in (n=6) knowledge holders: Aklavik (n=10), Fort McPherson (n=6), Tuktoyaktuk (n=3), and Inuvik (n=5). Interviews were conducted in English, lasted 60 to 90 minutes and were nearly gender-balanced (m=14, f=10). Most participants were over 40, reflecting extensive land-based experience (20–40 years: n=3; 40–60 years: n=11; 60+ years: n=10). One of the central questions of the interviews was “What does Permafrost mean to you?” The Gwich'in and Inuvialuit are distinct yet intertwined Indigenous Peoples, with specific histories and cultures, although many share a mixed ancestry. While the Inuvialuit are Inuit from the Western Arctic near the coastal region,

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area (Mackenzie Delta). By Rodrigue Tanguy, 2024.

the Gwich'in are a First Nation of Canada and part of the Dene family. Gwich'in participants emphasized permafrost in relation to soil stability, hydrology, and subsistence (hunting, berry harvesting). Inuvialuit participants also stressed coastal integrity, sea ice stability, and the risks of erosion and displacement. We conducted research in partnership with the Aklavik Hunters and Trappers Association, the Tuktoyaktuk Community Corporation, the Gwich'in Tribal Council's Department of Culture and Heritage, and the Imaryuk Monitoring Program along the ITH. As non-Indigenous researchers, we recognize our positionality: trust was facilitated through existing collaborations, but our interpretations remain shaped by disciplinary backgrounds and outsider status. Local partners guided and reviewed the design, ensuring a community-based, participatory approach (Ford et al. 2016). Indigenous Knowledge and local knowledge are empirically grounded in intergenerational observation and classification (Cruikshank 2012), prompting us to center participants' quotes² and everyday practices in our analysis. While findings are preliminary, they demonstrate that permafrost is experienced as lived materiality rather than a static object—an understanding crucial for more context-sensitive, collaborative, and Indigenous-led adaptation in the Arctic.

Perceptions of Permafrost (Thaw)

Ingold (2000 [2011]) argues that humans learn to perceive by receiving clues, a process he calls *enskilment*: the culturally specific capability to act and perceive, re-grown in each generation “through training and experience in the performance of particular tasks” (2000 [2011], 5). Perception is then also, in part, shaped by practical engagements with materials. In our case, permafrost is often experienced in conjunction with building activities: Johnnie Storr, an Aklavik resident, for example, referred to permafrost as simply the ice, or the “hard stuff” they encounter when they dig a hole in the ground during summertime: “It’s a big block of ice. I’ve run the excavator and we did all the ditching in the community and we’ve run into a lot of permafrost, there’s no way of digging through that. We’ve tried every which way!” Lennie Emaghok expressed how he uses it: “To me, I think it’s really important, I know where to find it. I have used it many times. I learned from my dad where to look for permafrost.” He knew its function and also observed its diminishment, “It is preserving the ground from crumbling. There is a foot of moss and muskeg that is the covering, but as soon as that layer is disturbed and exposes the permafrost, it goes. We have a lot of that.”

Such accounts align with Ingold (2000 [2011]) concept of *enskilment* as grounded in practice, activity and formation of perception. For Ingold, perception is “... an active and exploratory engagement of the whole person, indissolubly body and mind, in a richly structured environment” (2000 [2011], xvii), resulting “...from the reconstruction of naturally given realities in terms of metaphors drawn from the ideal realm of culture.” (2000 [2011], 10). While Ingold uses stories and songs as examples, it can be said that narratives more broadly convey perception. Cruikshank (1998, 2005) and Lichtenberg (2017) argue that it is through narratives that people attribute meaning and make sense of their experiences and the world around them. Our study participants’ narratives foreground many of the impacts associated with permafrost degradation.

Perception, Visibility and Ordinarity

Another lens to examine perceptions and meanings of permafrost are theories of infrastructure. Chu (2014), for example, points to two moments when infrastructures, typically considered ordinary, become visible: First, when they are introduced, either as icons of modernity (for example, Hughes 1983), and second, upon breakdown (for example, Star 1999)—or in this case, transformation. Until then, permafrost, as infrastructure in the classical sense (Landa 2016), is not

thought about much. However, it is important to note that permafrost landscape features, such as Pingos³, have historically been used as lookouts, for example; and mountainscapes, literally held together by permafrost, carry spiritual meaning. Mackenzie River Delta and Beaufort Sea Coast inhabitants consider their local ecology as a living, dynamic, relational whole, comprised of interacting elements—including permafrost—which must be attended to respectfully by humans (Krause 2021; Rose 2005). As the stable layer of permafrost increasingly deteriorates (Andrews et al. 2016; Burn and Kokelj 2009; Lantuit et al. 2012), inhabitants express their concern about permafrost itself:

Permafrost? We never really thought about it. Before, when we were out on the land, we never had problems with travelling. But when I think about us going for berries today, sometimes we have to walk quite a distance, and the softer ground is really a disadvantage to us. (Sarah Jerome)

When asked what permafrost meant to them, this young person said they knew it was there, but never gave it too much thought: “Ice in the ground, frozen ground, I know there is a lot around here, but never studied on it or read about it. I have never spent much time thinking about it.” (Grace Illasiak) Although some inhabitants actively use permafrost, and certain permafrost features carry meaning beyond simply being part of the land, for others, it only becomes visible through degradation.

Recent scientific attention to permafrost in the Mackenzie Delta has increased markedly, given global effects of climate change and the localized consequences of increased thaw (for example, Crate et al. 2017, Ramage et al. 2022, Ward Jones et al 2024). Through such knowledge transfer, permafrost is changing from being perceived as an intrinsic element of the land to a critical part. Visibility is varied and contingent upon geographical location, cosmologies and engagement with permafrost through labour (for example, construction work, home repairs, building ice houses/cellars) (Carse 2012, Star and Ruhleder 1996)—or land use (for example, subsistence, travelling across the land). For many, these changes are visible, and people continue to adapt as part of everyday life:

It’s changing our land, and you know, it’s just something that we see almost every day. We don’t understand everything about it, like scientifically, but with the changes we see, we understand, and you know, we live it. I mean, that’s just life for us. (Johnnie Storr)

Such sentiments reflect what Star (1999) argued, that infrastructure is perceived as unexciting. Our study participants emphasized that permafrost thaw is part of their everyday life and thereby not out of the ordinary. However, the tempo of that change is perceived differently.

Temporalities and Change

Our study participants understand the malleable nature of delta and coastal environments: “The banks have always eroded. That’s what deltas do, they shift, they move, they change” (Kylik Kisoun). In part, it is the tempo of that change that determines if it presents a problem. Krause (2021, 2), working in Aklavik, argues that “[w]hether a material is experienced as solid or fluid emerges in the tangling of different tempos of humans, technologies and materials.” If change occurs faster than people can adapt, then permafrost is considered unstable and a problem. If, however, the tempos of change and adaptation coincide, increased permafrost thaw may not be considered a particular challenge. Thus, what Star found about infrastructure applies to permafrost, namely that it “[...] is big, layered, and complex, and because it means different things locally, it is never changed from above. [...] Nobody is really in charge of infrastructure” Star (1999, 382). This complexity increases in the Mackenzie Delta, as deltas are extremely malleable environments that change constantly, whether or not permafrost thaw has increased. It can thus be challenging for people to differentiate between changes caused by increased thaw and those that are due to regular freeze/thaw cycles, normal variations within the delta and coastal systems, or poor construction practices.

To add to this complexity, several dimensions of temporality are at play here. First, the gradual tempo of change over many thousands of years affecting permafrost, and the annual freeze-thaw cycle of the active layer. Both processes are familiar to Arctic inhabitants. However, the third, much faster change is due to anthropogenic climate change. Adaptation to these changes is commonly seen as inevitable, reflected in statements such as “We have to adapt and live with it,” or “We have no choice but to adapt.” For construction, inhabitants are improving established practices and inventing new ways to work *with* thawing permafrost, for example, preparing the ground over several years before construction, stabilizing the river and lake banks, and protecting exposed permafrost banks with cut brushes. However, harnessing Indigenous and contemporary knowledge and technologies to develop new construction practices, which are, in fact, suitable for an Arctic permafrost environment, takes time, often interfering with established construction industry timeframes.

Inuvialuit and Gwich'in First Nation land users shared anxiety about failures in classical “hard” infrastructure—for roads, buildings and cabins,

Long ago, we never had problems when we did things. Now you build something on the ground, and it starts sinking. It's so different, there is no frost on the bottom, and the ground is sinking all over. You build something, it starts sinking, don't matter if it's big or small. (Nellie Arey)

Most of this infrastructure is along the coast and riverbanks, which are at higher risk due to flooding and erosion. Coastal erosion in Tuktoyaktuk is causing much emotional distress:

The people that had to relocate to a different location were raised beside the ocean. They so miss their original area they stayed in since they were born. My heart goes out to them because they live upland now, with no ocean view. Climate change has taken their original traditional area where their parents settled in Tuktoyaktuk. (Lena Kotokak)

Large sections of riverbanks can also erode suddenly, giving no opportunity to respond and creating widespread concern. In 2022, a piece of land more than a hundred meters wide suddenly fell near Elizabeth Gordon's cabin: “There's one corner in the channel there. A piece of land at least the size of the [hockey] arena fell in [to the river] just in a day or two.” These events impact land users and their ability to provide country food. Elizabeth commented,

We went back out to my cabin, and it [the piece of land] was gone. I was scared to go around the corner and see if my camp was still there! It's 300 feet wide, and 100 feet inland, and it was gone! We couldn't really do anything this summer because all we had to focus on is: Okay, our [river] banks are falling too much. It's scary!

Permafrost degradation processes thus have significant impacts on inhabitants' physical and mental health, as shown by our own and many others' examples (for example, Andrews et al. 2016, Ramage et al. 2022). According to Inuvialuit and Gwich'in First Nation land users and knowledge holders, environmental change began decades ago and has significantly accelerated in recent years. As mentioned before, what is crucial here is the relative tempo of transformation that permafrost (as a solid fluid) is undergoing in relation to human lives (Krause 2021). Building on Indigenous philosophies of land (for example, TallBear 2017, Watt-Cloutier 2015) and Lefebvre's notion of tempo (2004), Krause points out that physical transformations are experienced as either slow or (too) fast, depending on how they stand in relation to human

activities. The high mobility of Inuit and First Nations ways of life is challenged by even minor changes in the temperature of rivers, lakes, sea ice, the ocean, roads, trails, and tundra in the Mackenzie River Delta; and adaptation actions are manifold (Mosey 2024). If temperature increase accelerates, on the land activities, food security and the health of inhabitants are also jeopardized. Participants further expressed concern about the impact of permafrost thaw on cultural heritage along the coast (Andrews et al. 2016; Friesen 2015; Hollesen et al. 2018), such as old whaling cabins, Inuvialuit archeological sites and graves.

A fourth temporal dimension is the annual subsistence round, in this case, harvesting whales and fish in summer, and caribou, moose, geese and other waterfowl in spring and fall. The next section will discuss permafrost's role as critical and alimentary infrastructure in the sense that it provides the literal foundation of life in continuous permafrost regions.

Permafrost as Infrastructure (?)

Critical infrastructure

Ingold (2000 [2011]) argues that persons and things emerge within an unfolding field of relations, forming entanglements or a “meshwork” of lifelines. Indigenous scholar Anne Spice (2018, 41), drawing on Freda Huson, suggests that this web of relations between human and other-than-human beings sustaining Indigenous life can be understood as *critical infrastructure*. Seeing the environment as infrastructure that provides ecosystem services highlights the costs of degradation (Carse 2012), but this framing has been criticized as anthropocentric (Farley et al. 2024). An eco-centric approach instead recognizes humans as part of socio-ecological systems and embraces the roles of nonhumans (Farley et al. 2024; Washington et al. 2017). From this perspective, permafrost is part of critical infrastructure: integral to the land and inseparable from the lives it upholds. Inuvialuit and Gwich'in First Nation land users emphasize the fundamental character of permafrost, emphasizing its role for stability: “Permafrost is a block of ice that holds the foundation together. You know, and you put a little heat onto that ice cube, your foundation is going to slowly deplete—either fast or slow depending on how much heat energy it takes in.” (Richard Gordon) Permafrost can thus be considered part of life-sustaining “critical infrastructure” (Spice 2018) for people living on permafrost soils where the condition of the ground is crucial for subsistence. In the words of writer/ climate activist Mary Annaïse Heglar, “Today, I worry about permafrost the way I thought I was going to have to worry about quicksand when I was a

kid” (Heglar 2021). Richard Gordon explained this very concern as part of his everyday life,

Erosion is happening, and it affects travelling, because now you got to stay focused for the cliff or something that you may fall into. Using a skidoo one time up there, I was driving, looking at the land and thinking: that looks nice and smooth, I better go across there. Next thing I just sank, and ended up walking on the spongy ground. When I turned around to look at my skidoo, my skis were up in the air. It was just like quicksand.⁴ So those things are unpredictable, and that’s why you got to worry about the younger generation too.

Similarly, many participants emphasize the importance of permafrost and that you need to be more careful when moving on the land nowadays, particularly watching out for soft spots, which could be sinkholes. Permafrost thus affects the security of northern land users’ coupled socio-ecological system. It also influences the region’s hydrology, impacting water sources and quality, which are essential for daily life and livelihoods. Broadly, permafrost is a carbon sink which releases greenhouse gases as it thaws. Thus, given its roles, the stability and health of permafrost soils are critical for the overall well-being of both Arctic residents and global communities. In this way, “we all live on permafrost” (Crate 2021, 245). Many Northerners understand this:

Permafrost, it means stability for our land, our animals, our food, our water, everything. And if there’s an impact on the permafrost, then there will be so many different issues that could arise from that. Like, for example, you had to relocate. It’s already been happening. So, you have no more home. And that’s a big impact. And if it begins to have a warmer climate, then it affects the animals. And of course, we’re going to be affected because that’s what we live on: Our own animals that we have available to us. So that’s a big impact. And I think it not only impacts us, but it impacts everybody around the world. (Lena Kotokak)

Permafrost is thus seen as the literal foundation of life: In the continuous permafrost zone, everything, including homes, roads, and airstrips, is dependent upon it, which makes its stability crucial for infrastructure and life overall.

Permafrost as Alimentary Infrastructure

In rural Arctic settlements, food security is a combination of subsistence harvesting and access to affordable store-bought food. Participants shared their overall concern about the effects of thawing permafrost, based on their

Figure 2. Example of lake drainage in the Mackenzie Delta. Photo by Susanna Gartler (2024).

lived experience harvesting country foods: “Yeah, so, with the melting, it puts a big obstacle in our traditional harvesting.” The thawing makes the ground softer and moister, which affects hunting and berry picking: “It’s like you’re just walking on a big sponge now ... every step you’re sinking in at least six inches to a foot. That takes a lot out of you. It’s like walking in deep snow, you get tired.” (Johnnie Storr) Amongst many other species, muskrats are also affected: “A lot of the lakes are breaking through into the rivers and then they drain; and the muskrat have to move and find new lakes.” (Samuel McLeod; see Figure 2) Many also shared their concerns about the changes in fish and beaver populations, including related health concerns.

Concomitantly, rising food prices challenge households on limited budgets. Both permafrost thaw and rising prices are limiting their ability to feed their families. Johnnie Storr put it this way,

I don’t go out whaling to harvest fish and herring like other people do, but I do worry about the people of Aklavik. It’s getting so expensive now to make it down there [to the coast]. People really rely on those kinds of [country] foods. I’d usually go out and try to get as many caribou as I can in the fall to carry me through the winter. This year and last year,

I didn't get one caribou. I could really tell because I would go to the store every other day to buy some steaks or pork chops, or any kind of meat. And the price? The price here isn't cheap.

Land users talked about the ways they try and address the challenges of rising costs, often giving extra insight into the value of their country foods,

I did a comparison: On my way home from Edmonton, I bought CAD\$1,000 in meat. It filled the bottom of my freezer. If I were to buy CAD\$1,000 in gas and groceries for myself to go out hunting and harvesting, I could fill both of my freezers. (Johnnie Storr)

Historically and to some extent today, freezers have not been the only way to store food in cold regions. Ice houses, cellars or temporary pits dug in the frozen ground during hunting trips (Communities of Aklavik et al. 2005, Nyland et al. 2017, Saito et al. 2024) historically and today serve(d) as food storage infrastructures. In this sense, permafrost may quite literally be seen as (part of) infrastructure that is "... life-giving in its design, finance, and effects," i.e., *alimentary infrastructure* (LaDuke and Cowen 2020). Not only are ice houses and cellars functional, they also continue to be of cultural significance and inform Inuvialuit relations to their land (Inuit Circumpolar Council 2015, see also Pokiak 2020). Increased permafrost thaw has meant that many of these infrastructures no longer function properly.

In addition to providing food storage, permafrost is seen as a lifeline because it serves as the ecosystem's primary water source in an otherwise arid region. Several participants shared their understandings of and concerns for permafrost's role in the water cycle. The freeze-thaw cycle of permafrost means that the ice stored therein is part of the water supply. Inhabitants consider it a water-donor and thus life-giver, since polar regions receive very little precipitation over the course of the year:

The ice on top of the land gives us good berries. It feeds the berries and that. [It is] good because the water comes up or keeps water going in the soil. (Joanne Edwards Steen)

It's our lifeline here. Without the permafrost, this place doesn't exist. The culture of the region, the people wouldn't live here. It's the only reason why this place is green. The only reason why all these trees grow is because the permafrost is always unthawing and releasing water. And then the plants always have water. (Kylik Kisoun)

These quotes emphasize how important intact permafrost is not only to food security but also in terms of the ecosystem's water cycles. Thawing permafrost is a concern in the Inuvialuit Settlement Region and the Gwich'in Settlement Region, since contaminants may come from old oil and natural gas tailings stored underground. Warmer temperatures and thawing permafrost now threaten to release these pollutants, and potentially, infectious diseases, into the groundwater and soil. Additionally, air and water circulation patterns can bring external contaminants into the local ecosystem. Some residents thus experience uncertainty about the safety of their drinking water. To address these concerns, it is essential to regularly test residential drinking water and other sources, and to share this information in order to boost confidence in the water quality (Communities of Aklavik et al. 2005).

Subsistence harvesting relies on Arctic transport infrastructures such as roads and airstrips, but also frozen rivers and lakes during wintertime and navigable river channels and ocean conditions in summer. All are dependent on stable permafrost ground. The increasing impacts of permafrost degradation in combination with other physical drivers, such as erosion and storm surges, require the modification of travel routes. Hunters explain which changes they have seen in terms of the permafrost thawing in their lifetimes:

It's changing our river systems a lot. I've been travelling these rivers since I was small, and we used to travel by almost all the rivers down towards the coast. Now there's only one or two that you could make it through. There are cabins that were washed away all throughout the Delta. And it's just getting harder to travel out there every year. (Johnnie Storr)

It is one thing for experienced hunters and fishers to observe and adapt to conditions they have worked in for decades. But what about the new generation who are just going out on the land? Parents express concern that their knowledge of habitual travel routes cannot be passed on to future generations since change is occurring at such a rapid pace. Even if youth could learn historical routes, they will have to deal with more dangerous conditions, a concern expressed widely:

In a few years, we'll have to go straight out the ocean and come back into the smaller rivers [which] is a lot more dangerous, because of the winds that we've been getting and we're seeing a lot more flooding. It worries me that my boy would have to worry about those changes,

and it will be harder for him to access the traditional foods. When I'm travelling, I let them know. You know, like: "There used to be a place here and the river used to be a lot narrower here. And you gotta watch for these sandbars here." (Johnnie Storr)

Permafrost degradation also impacts airstrips and roads. A landslide, due to permafrost thaw, can easily block off the only road to the region, causing concern for food security in terms of store-bought items, as well. Along the Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway, several mitigation measures are being taken to alleviate impacts, such as gravel-filled sandbags along the roadsides to prevent water from running off the road. The Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway is an example of the kinds of promises roads can carry (see Anand, Gupta and Appel 2018; Mrázek 2002). LaDuke and Cowen (2020) reflect on the intricate relationship between infrastructure and coloniality, that is, the entanglement of settler-colonial projects with infrastructural mega-projects such as roads. Several years after the construction of this multi-million-dollar road, study participants voiced concerns about the adverse (permafrost-related) environmental, socio-cultural and/or economic impacts the road is having (Povoroznyuk et al. 2022).

I don't like that the permafrost is melting at some parts of the sections of the highway. I see, because I'm on the highway every day. And that I don't know if it's from the highway being built there. I think about it. Yeah. So that's what the permafrost is about. And living with it. (Joanne Edwards Steen)

This quote circles us back to examining permafrost through the lenses of perception and infrastructure, namely that it is becoming increasingly visible through failure and transformation. At the same time, this is seen as something ordinary in permafrost regions, where people engage and experience permafrost thaw impacts almost daily.

Discussion and Conclusion: A Thawing Relation

Our study shows that permafrost can be understood as a critical (Spice 2018) and alimentary (Laduke and Cowen 2020) infrastructure: the foundation of life in the far North, which itself is undergoing change. In relation to Anthropocene scholarship, which treats infrastructure primarily through the lens of decay and material breakdown (Hetherington 2019), our study both highlights how impacts of decaying permafrost perpetuate ongoing racialized power imbalances of settler colonialism (ibid.), as well as how Indigenous perspectives

draw attention to permafrost as inseparable from land, kinship, and sustenance. This engagement demonstrates how infrastructural analysis can be expanded by Indigenous epistemologies, producing new understandings of both infrastructure and environment in Arctic contexts. At the same time, we draw on theories of perception Ingold (2000 [2011]) and thereby build on developments in the relatively nascent field of anthropology and climate change. Beginning in the late 1990s, anthropologists began to focus on how people, in the context of their human-environment interactions, were witnessing, understanding and making sense of unprecedented change in their immediate environment (Crate and Nuttall 2009; 2016; 2024). However, the emphasis was not on how people acted in response, but rather on how they cognized the changes based on their worldview and beliefs. In other words, what their immediate environment meant to them and how they perceived what were for them novel changes to it. Here, we continue this exploration and examine not only the meaning attributed to permafrost itself but also how people perceive permafrost-related changes through the lens of infrastructure theorizing. By examining narratives derived from ethnographic interviews with twenty-four Indigenous knowledge holders and land users, we highlight the relationship between permafrost as foundational, alimentary and critical infrastructure and the continuation and vitality of Inuvialuit and Gwich'in life in the Mackenzie Delta.

Our research demonstrates how permafrost is a fundamental aspect upon which life in permafrost regions depends—and thus as critical, relational infrastructure. At the same time, we uncover variations in perception of the material itself, depending on people's interactions, experience, and occupations—or *enskilment*, using Ingold (2000 [2011]) term. Moreover, our study shows that until recently, permafrost was not a concern as long as its cycles remained unaltered, but the Indigenous peoples who use these lands have always had knowledge about it. It is only in the wake of bio-physical changes impacting everyday life, in conjunction with the global discourse on climate change, that its critical role is known. Finally, by foregrounding Indigenous perspectives, this article expands anthropological debates on infrastructure and contributes to the anthropology of climate change. It does so by exploring some of the meanings attributed to permafrost as a material and how Indigenous land users live and engage with the ever-changing landscape and the acceleration of change in the Inuvialuit Settlement Region and the Gwich'in Settlement Region of the Western Canadian Arctic. Conceptually speaking, Blok et al. (2016) suggest that *infrastructuring* brings together such

heterogeneous elements. In this way we contribute to infrastructuring permafrost environments, by attending to ways of knowing and acting upon permafrost—thus highlighting some of the heterogeneous socio-cultural, political, natural and material relations permafrost entails; and describing “... situated realities rather than epochal change... adding to theoretical work as the work of proposing new layers and articulations” (Blok et al. 2016, 3).

Coming back to our central research question, “What does permafrost mean to Inuvialuit and Gwich’in knowledge holders in the Mackenzie River Delta and Beaufort Sea region,” we argue that our empirical material describing situated realities provides nascent insights into these heterogeneous relations. Our central results, or new layers and articulations, entail a number of insights into how permafrost is perceived, and which meanings are attributed to it by Indigenous land users in the Western Canadian Arctic. We find that permafrost is primarily perceived through *enskilment* Ingold (2000 [2011]), entailing ethnically specific land use—such as berry picking, hunting, whaling, fishing—and labour or occupation. It is also contingent on other factors such as the physical characteristics of permafrost, and types of landscapes (mountainous terrain, delta environments, coastal areas, etcetera). Differences in perceptions appear between individuals, where distinct aspects are highlighted by different people depending on the factors mentioned above. Some consider it a source of life as it supplies water to an otherwise arid region. Others foreground its solidity in relation to construction projects, such as building cabins—or highlight the fact that the ground can become a treacherous trap that one could become ensnared in, akin to what sinking into quicksand is conceived of in the popular imagination. Moreover, permafrost and permafrost thaw impacts are perceived distinctively by the culturally different yet intertwined groups. Thus, following Star’s (1999) argument about infrastructures’ divergent local meanings, permafrost carries a multitude of meanings, serving as an omnipresent and literally foundational material that becomes increasingly noticeable as it is exposed to rising temperatures and undergoes more extensive thawing. However, permafrost is becoming increasingly visible (Chu 2014, Star 1999) not just through landscape transformations such as softer, wetter tundra, changes in river systems, riverbank and coastal erosion, slumping, and so on, but also because of the increased attention it receives both from scientific communities and the media. At the same time, permafrost, as well as constant change(s), retain their ordinariness, qualified as part of everyday life.

Permafrost stands for stability and is reflected upon as a relational foundation for human and more-than-human life in the Mackenzie Delta, and can thus be characterized as critical infrastructure in the sense of Spice (2018, according to Huson). The connection between people and permafrost is relational in the sense that permafrost thaw is impacting animal migration routes, housing, food and water security, mobility, knowledge transmission, and thus relationships to self and kin, whether human or otherwise. Permafrost's role in food and water security draws a parallel to the concept of alimentary infrastructure (LaDuke and Cowen 2020), specifically in relation to food storage (ice houses, ice cellars), but also subsistence activities more broadly, which depend on predictable conditions and intact coupled socio-ecological systems. Land and permafrost are then part of this "most immediate material and graspable form" of infrastructure, underpinning and enacting sustenance and reproduction (LaDuke and Cowen 2020, 264), enabling life in a decolonial, indigenizing context. Permafrost is then alimentary, critical and foundational infrastructure, in the sense of what is geologically assembled below the surface and enables wholesome Indigenous ways of dwelling and movement on the land.

Permafrost can also be likened to infrastructure in the sense that no one is really in charge of it (see Star 1999), and changes—and adaption to them—are seen as inevitable. At the same time, acting upon permafrost-related change(s) and the multiple temporalities at play depends on the relative tempos of change (Krause 2021). The escalated thawing of permafrost in the Mackenzie Delta is causing numerous adverse effects, for example, on the water supply for the more-than-human ecology of the land, but also to infrastructure and mobility. This points toward (failed) promises (Larkin 2013), coloniality and dependence entrenched in infrastructural projects (Hetherington 2019, LaDuke and Cowen 2020). As Arctic transport infrastructures, including roads, river systems and trails, are impacted, intergenerational knowledge transfer is disrupted. Such negative consequences can be seen as a continuation of colonial violence against the Indigenous Peoples of the North, since warming temperatures and thawing ground are caused by the aggressive expansion of imperial-capitalist systems of domination fuelled by carbon-intensive industries and energy consumption. To conclude, examining perceptions of permafrost and related processes through the lens of infrastructure theories proves useful and generative in a number of ways. However, further research with larger sample sizes and including community members from more settlements in the Inuvialuit and

Gwich'in Settlement Regions is necessary to complement and deepen this first exploration of what permafrost means to Inuvialuit and Gwich'in First Nation knowledge holders.

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Notes

- 1 Continuous permafrost refers to a zone where permafrost underlies nearly the entire landscape, typically covering more than 90% of the ground surface. It is most common in the coldest regions of the Arctic and Subarctic, where mean annual air temperatures are well below 0 °C, and the active layer thaws only seasonally. (French 2018)
- 2 The quotes have been revised for readability. Note that the language of some of the older participants reflects that they grew up with an Indigenous language as their mother tongue.
- 3 “The word ‘pingo’ is of local Inuit origin and is used to describe an ice-cored conical hill in the Mackenzie Delta, Canada.” (French 2018, 159).
- 4 The phenomenon participants describe here is known as soil liquefaction, which occurs when the pressure of the water (pore fluid) in the ground becomes equal to the pressure holding the sediment particles together.

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